

THE CHALLENGES OF DIGITAL PRESERVATION SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION IN A GALLERY SETTING

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Abstract – Over the last two years, the Art Gallery of New South Wales (The Gallery) has undergone significant changes in their digital preservation program. The Gallery went from being a member of a consortium project with other cultural institutions using a common SIP specification based on PREMIS 3.0, to going it alone and completing a procurement process resulting in Preservica as our chosen digital preservation system.

This paper will outline how the uniqueness of the Gallery collection warranted the pivot from shared system and storage solution to separate digital preservation system and the challenges of implementation so far.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The Art Gallery of New South Wales (The Gallery) established a digital preservation team in 2021 with a mandate to procure a dedicated digital preservation system and appropriate storage, to ensure the preservation of their digital collection. Having completed an expression of interest request to market in 2022, the team was working with internal stakeholders to define the scope of the collection, identify file locations and mapping appropriate metadata.

The Gallery joined the NSW Government funded initiative in 2022, known as the Cluster Digital Restart Fund (Cluster DRF) pilot project, investigating the viability of a shared digital preservation system and storage solution consortium between four Cultural Institutions. The consortium members included the State Library of New South Wales (SLNSW), the Gallery, Australian Museum (AM) and Sydney Opera House (SOH) [1]. As each institution was at a different level of digital preservation maturity, the project developed a common SIP specification based on PREMIS 3.0 so that all contributing institutions could package and ingest their material with required metadata regardless of complexity [2]. This was advantageous for the Gallery as our collection contains different collection sets including complex time-based artworks, collected archives and institutional records. Mapping to the common SIP specification meant that we were across how well PREMIS and METS schemas aligned with our organisational minimum metadata requirements and could carry that knowledge over to our own system implementation.

In 2024, following the end of our involvement in the Cluster DRF pilot project, The Gallery completed a procurement process for a dedicated digital preservation system, Preservica. Preservica was chosen for its highly flexible packaging formats and metadata schema support. This makes it suitable for

the ingestion of collections on a case-by-case basis for simple directories of text files, as well as covering complex archives, institutional records, and time-based artworks. The system also presented the flexibility needed to cover the representation of software and hardware as Environmental Entities within the system for preservation and future emulation considerations.

II. DATA MODEL AND METADATA MAPPING

The Gallery collection is comprised of TBA, collected archives, collection documentation and institutional archives. Each has different core metadata fields within their Collection Management System (CMS) record and some, as is the case with institutional archives, may not currently be represented in a CMS. A key part of the DRF project was mapping out how we would structure our collection using the PREMIS metadata schema. This is to ensure that the original structure of the content is maintained and reflects our internal data model, which defines the Gallery representation types such as Acquisition Package and Preservation Master, and the key metadata fields.

To do so we had to grapple with Preservica's digital transfer packaging formats: Open Preservation Exchange (OPEX) and Preservation Asset Exchange (PAX). OPEX is designed for the transfer of structured digital preservation content with optional descriptive metadata and transfer verification (manifests and checksums) in metadata files. The PAX format is a transferable representation of complex or multi-part assets. It can be a single logical asset comprising multiple files in a multi-part representation, or a migrated asset that has multiple generations of content or multiple representations. [3]

These packages are based on two key principles:

- Flexibility. There are no mandatory metadata elements and only the relevant or available metadata needs to be specified.
- Content can be transferred in an incremental and modular manner (as metadata fragments), so you do not have to wait for the entire content to be ready before ingesting it.

A. KEY CHALLENGES

While the Gallery is not the first or only Preservica customer in Australia, as an art museum, our collection includes complex time-based

artworks, collected Archives, as well as Gallery created content. Much of The Gallery's Institutional collection is either not catalogued in a collection management system (CMS) or has been subject to inconsistent cataloguing. The Gallery has an ongoing agreement with State Records NSW to self-manage our institutional records. Organisational rollout and use of records software Content Manager has been limited and continued use of this software, and the application of our Business Classification Scheme (BCS) is currently being reviewed. This means that our digital institutional records have inconsistencies when it comes to naming conventions and appropriate identifiers, making it difficult to automate and streamline ingest processes.

With this context in mind, while the advice and experience of other institutions using Preservica is helpful, many have established workflows developed over many years that are purpose-built with their collections and organisational policies in mind. Scripts, SIP packages and ingest portals can vary widely and many have not needed to contend with and test OPEX and PAX transfer formats in the same way that the Gallery does. [3]

B. PROPOSED SOLUTION – IDENTIFIERS

With many different systems and identifiers (or lack thereof), we needed a consistent way of identifying material from ingest to preservation within the Preservica system. This is important for future considerations of system migrations and exit strategies. We outlined the various identifiers that the Gallery currently uses, their structure and how important they are to our collection management processes. These include accession numbers within Vernon CMS, exhibition and photography identifiers within Fotoware Digital Asset Management System (DAMS) and Archival Manuscript and Box numbers. We discovered quite a lot of inconsistencies including Vernon allowing for repeatable System identifiers (SIDs) between Object and Person Datafiles, collection photography assets having their own filename and identifier based on the collection type, and event and exhibition photography using a different identifier entirely.

While Preservica does generate its own Type 4 Globally Unique Identifier (GUID), to maintain consistency with existing identifiers for system migration considerations, we decided to create a

unique identifier that we could use across all the collections.

In researching the potential use of existing identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOI), Uniform Resource Name (URN) or Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), we found that each option had some limitations and did not meet our needs. These include being designed for a particular industry, such as scientific or academic research, or failing to secure against the risk of broken links. We decided that the use of Archival Resource Keys (ARKs) would be the best identifier as it incorporates an organisationally unique Name Assigning Authority Number (NAAN), can be used with or without an organisational resolver for links, can be implemented locally with open-source tools, are human-readable and can be integrated with other systems.

As The Gallery plans to use Preservica as a dark archive, we will use the NAAN to develop our own identifier that can integrate into our current and future web design for access purposes.

The NAAN integrates with our Data Model and offers human readable elements helpful for ongoing collection management. The result is a Powershell script which incorporates the 'AGNSW Collection Term', such as 'Time-based artwork' or 'Collected archive' alongside the NAAN, plus a 10-digit random numeric string for ongoing collection accessions into the future.

- **Write-Output ("AGNSW Collection Term_" + "_AGNSW NAAN_" + (Get-Random -Minimum 100000000 -Maximum 999999999))'.**

C. PROPOSED SOLUTION – DATA MODEL

For our data model, the first step was defining and documenting the key Intellectual Entity (IE) representation types across our collections. Then, using the Cluster DRF project Common SIP specification, we started to actively map our collection and institutional material from intellectual entity to file level. With the procurement of Preservica, we looked at how to transform the PREMIS elements mapped via the Common SIP specification, to OPEX and PAX elements and determining the minimum metadata elements for each collection type. These are sourced from Vernon CMS for the time-based artwork (TBA), Collected Archives and Content Manager for the

Institutional records. The result is a Data Model based on PREMIS 3.0, that will incorporate Environmental Entities, combined with flexibility of the Preservica's OPEX and PAX.

Consulting with Preservica and other users showed how we can represent our material within the system. This increased our understanding of how the metadata is represented and searched at the various levels of Structural Object (SO- the SIP package), Information Object (the Intellectual Entity level), Representation, Content Object and Bitstream Levels. While other institutions clarified how to potentially structure our SIPs and the automated options for packaging and ingestion, many were not using OPEX and PAX structures, or had more uniform and simplified collection sets.

Due to the complexities of TBA, we would need to ingest multiple representation types and link them as part of the same SIP at the Structural Object level. As Preservica automatically applies either a 'Preservation' or 'Access' representation for each Information Object ingested into the system, we would need to ingest each representation type as an Information Object within the same SO to most easily represent all representation types while maximising metadata searchability.

The key representation types are:

- **Acquisition Package.** This is a copy of all the material provided by the artist at the time of acquisition.
- **Preservation Master.** Master preservation files from which Modified Masters are made.
- **Digital Original.** Born-digital original master files, for when files have been normalised to create the Preservation Master. No preservation actions are to be performed on this type.
- **Display Master.** These are exhibition files by year which have been transcoded or edited in a way which means they are useful to retain.
- **Related Reference.** Information that is integral to the interpretation of the work but is not a collection item itself. These could include Finding Aids, iteration reports, certificate of authenticity, or artwork testing reports.

- **Technical Reference.** Reference images created to define image capture or specific metadata information. These include Operating System (OS) requirements or transcode specifications.

The Preservation Master Representation is mandatory and an Acquisition Package is expected for most artworks. These would be ingested according to the following structure (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Map showing how the Preservica Data Model maps to the Gallery Data Model for use within Preservica.

III. TESTING

The Gallery will be operating Preservica with a hybrid storage model. Preservica is hosted by AWS and we will be creating three preservation copies, one local “on-prem” copy, one AWS and one Azure blob.

Sample SOs were created using our Data Model including both OPEX and PAX files. This tested the validity of our OPEX and PAX files, whether the metadata would ingest as expected and was searchable, as well as the load capacity of the current ICT infrastructure and incoming AWS and Azure storage solutions. This also included whether the Sandbox and Production assets are appropriately separated in the back-end.

Browser limits caused time-outs for large files so it was decided the primary ingestion method would be incremental ingest to the S3 bucket using

Cloudberry. Although the ingestion was successful, it took a significant amount of time, due to sequential looped processing of each workflow instance, as well as the capped gallery-wide connection to the internet shared by all staff.

IV. NEXT STEPS

Next steps will be setting up ingest automation using scripting and APIs to extract, package and ingest material. The Gallery will investigate the best way to represent software and hardware environments (Environmental Intellectual Objects) within Preservica for future emulation and access.

V. CONCLUSION

This process has enabled us to refine our data model and SIP packaging, identify key gaps in cataloguing and influence improvements to Gallery workflows that are producing key points of metadata. Starting with PREMIS mapping of our collection, we have been able to incorporate dedicated and shared representations of software and hardware environments within the digital preservation system.

While best practice and community collaboration assistance have been helpful, the unique organisational challenges of being an artist led art museum, with complex TBA collections, will determine how to move forward and to what degree custom system development will be needed.

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